

NanoBio4Can NEWSLETTER - Vol.1 -

PUBLICATION NEWS

Peptide-Functionalized Liposomal Nanocarriers

A collaborative open access review article led by Kashif Maroof, PhD a NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral Programme Fellow, under the supervision of Rukan Genç Altürk, PhD, and co-authored with Ronald Fook Seng Lee, PhD and Pinar Karacabey, has been published in ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science.

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Liposomal nanoparticles as a drug delivery system for improved treatment of multiple myeloma

An open-access review article led by Nemany A.N. Hanafy, Ph.D., a NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral Programme Fellow at KUTTAM, Koç University, under the supervision of Safacan Kolemen, Ph.D. (Koç University), has been published in RSC Advances.

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PUBLIC TALKS

The students of Terakki Foundation Schools meet with NanoBio4Can Researchers at SUNUM

On January 14, 2026, we hosted students and teachers from Terakki Foundation Private Şişli Terakki Science High School, and on January 14, 2026, from Terakki Foundation Private Şişli Terakki Anatolian High School at SUNUM.

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Saint-Michel French High School Students Meet with Researchers

On December 1, 2025, we hosted students from İstanbul Private Saint-Michel French High School at SUNUM.

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Eyüboğlu Education Institution Students Meet with Researchers

On November 18, 2025, we hosted students from Eyüboğlu Education Institutions at SUNUM.

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TRAINING

TÜBİTAK MAM hosted two workshops for NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund Fellows

TÜBİTAK MAM hosted a two-day workshop entitled "BD FACS CANTO II Flow Cytometry System Training" on 13-14 October 2025 at the TÜBİTAK MAM Biotechnology Research Group Labs for NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund fellows. The workshop was supported by Ant Medikal.

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NanoBio4Can Workshop at SUNUM

SUNUM hosted a one-day workshop entitled "Binding & Uptake Quantification in Targeted Drug Delivery Systems" on October 23, 2025 for NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund fellows.

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MSCA co-funded fellows participated Autophagy Practical Course and Workshop

NanoBio4can MSCA co-funded fellows Ankush D. Sontakke, Ika Nurlaila, Melike Belenli Gümüş, Nemany Abdelhamid Nemany Hanafy, Saif Ullah Afridi, and Shoeb Anwar Ansari participated in the Autophagy Practical Course and Workshop held at KUTTAM on 25-26.09.2025.

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BLOG

NanoBio4Can's Blog is Live!

The first group of articles was published on the NanoBio4Can Blog, where fellows share articles related to their projects.

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VIDEO

NanoBio4Can Video Shooting

As part of the communication activities for NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund project, "Nano-Biotechnologies for Innovative Therapeutic Approaches in Cancer," we have launched a video series aimed at showcasing our researchers' projects to the public and bringing nanotechnology-based cancer research to a broad audience.

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UP COMING

NanoBio4Can 2nd Call Results Announced

The 2nd call results of the NanoBio4Can Project, a research and training fellowship programme for postdoctoral researchers aiming to develop Nano-Biotechnologies for Innovative Therapeutic Approaches in Cancer, have been announced.

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nanobio4can>

<https://www.instagram.com/nanobio4can/>

<https://nanobio4can.net/>

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